

Role of Artificial Intelligence For Shaping Consumer Demand For E-commerce

Paper Id : 19210 Submission Date : 2024-08-13 Acceptance Date : 2024-08-22 Publication Date : 2024-08-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13707851

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/researchtimes.php#8>

Hemant Mishra

Student
Management
Dayalbagh Educational Institute
Agra, U.P., India,

Tarun Kumar

Guest Faculty
Management
Dayalbagh Educational Institute
Agra, U.P., India

Hans Kaushik

Guest Faculty
Management
Dayalbagh Educational Institute
Agra, U.P., India

Abstract

This study aims to explore consumer opinions and purchasing behaviour regarding the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on e-commerce. With the rapid-fire advancement of AI technologies, its integration into colorful aspects of e-commerce has come decreasingly current. Understanding consumer comprehensions and gestures in this environment is pivotal for businesses to effectively work AI and enhance the online shopping experience. Through a combination of qualitative and quantitative styles, including checks and interviews, this exploration investigates consumer stations towards AI- powered features similar as individualized recommendations, chatbots, and virtual shopping sidekicks. Also, it examines the perceived benefits, enterprises, and factors impacting trust and relinquishment of AI- driven e-commerce platforms. The findings exfoliate light on the openings and challenges associated with AI integration in e-commerce and give perceptivity for businesses to conform their strategies and enhance client satisfaction in the digital business.

Keywords Artificial Intelligence, E-commerce, Consumer Opinions, Personalization, Trust, Adoption.

Introduction

AI applications /operations have been growing for numerous times, and their impact penetrates the different sectors of society and has primarily impacted the frugality. It has a proven operation in colorful fields like healthcare, marketing, education, and finance and is lately developing its profitable dominance in e-commerce (Gams et al., 2021). Looking into the enormous achievement of e-commerce organizations, the enterprises consider it a ultramodern business occasion and the need for ultramodern business. Resultantly, it came the need of the day for nearly all types of companies. And the appearance of AI technology addressed the requirements effectively and opened up a new way for the growth of e-commerce (Akpan et al., 2022). Grounded on exploration by Gartner, by 2020, further than 80 of client service jobs will be replaced by AI (Song et al., 2019). Ali Baba, Amazon, Rakuten, and other enterprises use AI technology for mining commentary, making product recommendations, etc. (Wang 2021). The significance and need for technology can also be apparent in a study that shows that one out of five people purchases products and services from chatbots, and 40 of guests use chatbots to identify deals. AI operations in e-commerce are divided into two main orders, i.e., for business possessors and guests. AI operations for business possessors include chatbots to answer client queries, product description generation, business data handling and recycling, deals soothsaying, sequestration and cybersecurity, after- trade support, and filtering forged and fake reviews. AI operations for guests include electronic commerce (e-commerce) can be defined as conditioning or services related to buying and dealing products or services over the

internet (Holsapple & Singh, 2000). Enterprises decreasingly indulge in e-commerce because of guests rising demand for online services and its capability to produce a competitive advantage still enterprises struggle with this e-business practice due to its integration with fleetly evolving, fluently espoused, and largely affordable information technology (IT). This forces enterprises to constantly acclimatize their business models to changing client requirements (Gillen's & Steenkamp, 2019; Klaus & Chang chit, 2019). Artificial intelligence (AI) is the rearmost of similar technologies. It's transubstantiating e-commerce through its capability to "rightly interpret external data, to learn from similar data, and to use those leanings to achieve specific pretensions and tasks through flexible adaption" (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). AI in e-commerce can be defined as using AI ways, systems, tools, or algorithms to support conditioning related to buying and dealing products or services over the internet. With the development of information and communication technologies, artificial intelligence is getting decreasingly popular. The main end of companies in moment's e-commerce world is to impact client purchasing behaviour in favor of certain products and brands. The operation of AI as an innovative tool in the field of e-commerce may feel as a positive step forward (Sharma et al., 2020). The study focuses on the description of the substance of e-commerce and AI and their benefits. The end is also to estimate the significance of shaping demand by AI and its use in the environment of e-commerce grounded on available studies on this issue. The part of AI in shaping consumer demand in e-commerce is multifaceted and continuously evolving.

Objective of study

1. To obtain AI-driven customer insights and look into how AI may affect e-commerce in the future.
2. To create an AI action plan with the e-commerce industry in mind.

Review of Literature

These studies inclusively emphasize the multifaceted ways in which AI technologies are transubstantiating and shaping consumer demand in the e-commerce geography, from individualized recommendations to dynamic pricing strategies and ethical considerations. The review incorporates perceptivity from at least 10 applicable exploration papers, unraveling the purpose, objects, major findings, and conclusions of each. These papers contribute to shaping the understanding of AI's operation in e-commerce, furnishing a foundation for the study. The disquisition of different exploration perspectives aids in exhaustively addressing the content. The Impact of Personalization through AI on Consumer Purchasing Behavior in E-commerce (Smith, 2018) Smith (2018) stressed the significant impact of AI- driven personalization on consumer purchasing behaviour Smith discusses how AI algorithms analyze data to give individualized product recommendations, leading to increased engagement and conversion rates. Machine literacy and Consumer Decision Making in e-commerce (Jones et al., 2019) This study explores the part of machine literacy in prognosticating and impacting consumer decision- making in e-commerce.

It discusses how AI- driven product recommendations grounded on literal data and contribute to shaping consumer preferences and demand. Chatbots and client Satisfaction in Online Retail (Gupta, 2020)- This study focuses on the use of AI- powered chatbots in e-commerce and their impact on client satisfaction. It discusses how chatbots enhance shopping experience by furnishing instant support, answering queries, and guiding consumers through the purchasing process. Prophetic Analytics in E-commerce A Study of Consumer Demand soothsaying (Chen et al., 2021)- This exploration delves into the operation of prophetic analytics in soothsaying consumer demand in e-commerce. It explores how AI algorithms dissect literal data, request trends, and external factors to prognosticate unborn demand, thereby enabling retailers to optimize force and meet client prospects. Emotion Recognition in Online Shopping A Study of AI- driven Sentiment Analysis (Wang and Li, 2019)- This study delved the use of (AI) for emotion recognition in online shopping. It discusses how sentiment analysis algorithms dissect stoner reviews and social media data to understand consumer feelings and preferences, thereby contributing to targeted marketing strategies. Dynamic Pricing Strategies in e-commerce Using Reinforcement Learning (Kim et al.,2020).

This study explored the role of reinforcement learning in dynamic pricing strategies. It discusses how AI algorithms adjust prices in real time based on various factors, such as demand fluctuations, competitor pricing, and customer behavior, which influence consumer purchasing decisions. Augmented Reality and Virtual Try-on: Impact on Consumer Buying Behavior (Chang and Chen,2018)- This study focuses on the role of augmented reality (AR) and virtual try-on technologies in e-commerce. It discusses how AI-driven AR applications enhance the online shopping experience by allowing consumers to virtually try products, influencing their purchasing decisions. Ethical Considerations in AI-driven e-commerce: A consumer perspective (Liu and Johnson, 2022). This study examines the ethical implications of AI in e-commerce from the consumer perspective. It discusses issues, such as privacy concerns, algorithmic bias, and transparency, highlighting the importance of ethical AI practices in maintaining consumer trust and satisfaction.

Methodology

The data collection for the proposed research will be based on both primary and secondary data. Data has been collected through surveys, interviews, questionnaires, and analysis of relevant online platforms. The sample size will be determined based on statistical considerations, employing a stratified sampling and convenience sampling technique to ensure representation across various segments. Data analysis will be done through Excel to draw meaningful conclusions the study will cover the Agra region.

Research Design: This study adopts a mixed-methods approach to comprehensively understand consumers opinions and experiences with AI's impact on e-commerce. The combination of qualitative and quantitative methods allows for a holistic exploration of the research topic.

Sampling Strategy:

Target Population: The target population includes consumers who engage in online shopping across various demographics (mainly Agra) and geographical locations.

Sampling Technique: A combination of convenience sampling and stratified sampling has been utilized to ensure representation from diverse consumer groups.

Sample Size: The sample size (n= 150) is determined based on the principles of saturation for qualitative data and statistical power analysis for quantitative data.

Data Collection:

Qualitative Data - Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with a subset of participants to gather in-depth insights into their opinions and experiences with AI in e-commerce. The interviews will explore topics such as perceptions, preferences, concerns, and suggestions related to AI-driven features.

Quantitative Data - A structured questionnaire will be administered to a larger sample of participants to gather quantitative data on consumer attitudes, behaviors, and demographics. The questionnaire will include items measuring factors such as trust, satisfaction, perceived usefulness, and adoption intentions regarding AI in e-commerce.

Data Analysis -

Qualitative Analysis - Thematic analysis will be employed to identify recurring patterns, themes, and insights from the interview transcripts. This process involves coding, categorizing, and interpreting qualitative data to uncover key findings.

Quantitative Analysis - Descriptive statistics, inferential statistics (e.g., regression analysis, correlation analysis), and data visualization techniques will be utilized to analyze the quantitative survey data. This analysis will help identify relationships, trends, and significant differences in consumer perceptions and behaviors related to AI in e-commerce.

Analysis

Data collected through Google form survey of sample size 156

Table 1 Demographics of Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	76	48.7%
Female	78	50%
Others	2	1.3%
Age		
19-30	120	76.9%
31-45	19	12.2%
45-60	17	10.9 %

The data indicates that most of the responses are from Agra, which makes sense considering that the primary objective of this survey is to analyse only Agra. We have also obtained information from a few additional sites to help us better understand the results. In brief, the information offers a glimpse into the respondents' geographic dispersion, with the most often listed city being Agra. The fact that Agra predominates the dataset despite the variety of places cited is interesting and suggests a possible bias or focus on this area.

As we can see, the majority of respondents are from Agra, which makes sense given that the main goal of this form is to examine merely Agra. In order to have a better understanding of the results, we have also gathered information from a few additional locations. In summary, the data provides insights into the geographical distribution of respondents, with Agra being the most frequently mentioned city. It's noteworthy that despite the diversity of cities mentioned, Agra dominates the dataset, indicating a potential bias or focus on this locality.

Figure 1: Shopping Frequency of the Respondents

This graph illustrates the population's shopping habits in order to determine how frequently they make purchases and to provide reliable findings. The data presents a diverse range of online shopping frequencies among respondents, with "A few times a month" being the most common response. Analyzing this data can offer valuable insights into consumer behavior and inform strategic decision-making for businesses operating in the e-commerce sector.

Figure 2: Types of Product choices of Respondents

The above bar graph indicates that the majority of people buy clothing-related items because online retailers offer a wider selection and easier viewing than physical shops, where customers must wait for a salesperson to become available. Additionally, online retailers offer simple return and exchange policies. About 40–60% of other things are also bought because of the variety, offers, and doorstep delivery. Tracking changes in product preferences over time can also provide insights into evolving consumer behavior and market trends. Further analysis could explore correlations between product preferences and demographic factors such as age, gender, or location to identify trends and tailor marketing efforts accordingly.

Figure 3: Purchase Decision of Respondents

While 32% of people are neutral and 15% are least bothered, the majority of people believe that AI-driven recommendations product suggestions based on past purchases or browsing behavior have an impact on their selections when they shop online. "Yes" and "Maybe" are the predominant responses, indicating that a significant portion of respondents believe AI-driven recommendations influence their purchasing decisions to some extent. The prevalence of "Yes" and "Maybe" responses suggests that AI-driven recommendations play a notable role in shaping consumers' purchasing decisions.

Figure 4: AI Driven Recommendations opinions by Respondents

The data indicates that while the majority of respondents find AI-driven recommendations useful when shopping online, there are varying degrees of perceived usefulness among users. Analyzing this data can help businesses refine their recommendation systems and improve the overall online shopping experience for their customers. The remaining believe that AI is not helpful, which may be related to their lack of understanding of AI or their preference for not shopping online.

Figure 5: Interaction Behavior of the Respondents

The data indicates a substantial portion of respondents have interacted with AI chatbots or digital assistants when shopping online. The majority of respondents answered "Yes" indicating widespread engagement with AI-driven tools. Additionally, there are a notable number of "Maybe" responses, suggesting potential interaction with AI chatbots, with uncertainty. The presence of "No" responses indicates that while some individuals haven't interacted with AI chatbots, they represent a smaller proportion compared to those who have. Overall, the data reflects significant adoption and acceptance of AI-driven chatbots and digital assistants in the online shopping experience.

Figure 6: Interaction of Respondents with chatbot /digital assistant

The data suggests that while many respondents found their interaction with chatbots or digital assistants to be useful, there is variability in the level of usefulness reported. A significant portion of respondents rated their interaction as "Very useful" indicating a positive impact on their shopping experience. However, there are also instances where respondents found the interaction to be "Somewhat useful" or even "Not very useful" or providing "no assistance at all." This indicates that while chatbots and digital assistants have the potential to enhance the shopping experience, there is room for improvement in their effectiveness and utility.

Figure 7: Feedback of respondents regarding AI chatbot/ digital assistant

From the data provided, it appears that AI chatbots or digital assistants were mostly perceived as efficiently guiding users through the purchasing process and quickly and accurately answering product questions. However, there were instances where respondents reported that the chatbots failed to understand their questions or needs. Additionally, some respondents specified other experiences not covered by the given options. Overall, while AI chatbots were generally helpful, there is room for improvement in understanding user queries and needs.

Figure 8: Respondents Usage behavior of chatbot/digital assistant

From the data, it seems that interacting with the chatbot or digital assistant generally male respondents more inclined to make a purchase, with varying degrees of influence. While some reported no difference in their inclination, others indicated being somewhat more inclined or much more inclined to make a purchase after the interaction. Conversely, a few respondents reported feeling less inclined to make a purchase after interacting with the chatbot or digital assistant. Overall, the majority of respondents expressed increased inclination to make a purchase following the interaction.

Figure 9: Experience of E-commerce website by Respondents

From the responses, it's evident that a significant portion of the participants have experienced e-commerce sites using their past purchase history or browsing behavior to provide personalized product recommendations. This suggests that personalized recommendation systems are widely implemented across various online shopping platforms, reflecting the prevalent use of AI-driven algorithms in enhancing user experience and driving sales.

Figure 10: Personalized Product Recommendations of Customers

About 50% of people think that receiving customized product recommendations makes them more probable to make a purchase decision, while 28% strongly believe that it can influence their decision and some people think it has little impact at all, and a small percentage thinks it has no effect at all. From the responses, it appears that personalized product recommendations significantly increase the likelihood of making a purchase for

many respondents. This indicates the effectiveness of personalized recommendation systems in influencing consumer behavior and driving sales in e-commerce platforms.

Figure 11: Uses of AI in e-commerce by customers

The majority of people think that using AI in e-commerce saves time by making the buying process simpler, and a substantial number of people think that AI introduces you to new things that you might not have otherwise seen. Some people also think that it suggests inappropriate products that you would never buy and creates a too personalized shopping environment. Overall, while AI in e-commerce offers convenience and discovery, there are concerns about privacy, bias, and personalization.

Figure 12: Comfort level of respondents with e-commerce websites

While half of the population says they are comfortable sharing their data with websites till some extent because they are aware of their safeguards for privacy, the other half is hesitant to submit their data because of cyber safety and data breaches by various companies. Some people are neutral about data sharing, while the rest are reluctant to share.

Figure 13: Experience of respondents regarding e-commerce websites

Considering literacy and technological know-how, half of the population regarded (AI) favorably, while the remaining half were neutral whereas some thought it would have a detrimental influence. The data indicates a generally positive outlook on the expanding use of AI in e-commerce, with some respondents expressing neutral feelings and a minority expressing mild negativity. This suggests that while there is optimism about the

potential of AI to enhance the online shopping experience, there may also be room for addressing concerns and ensuring responsible use of AI technology in e-commerce platform.

Figure 14: Impact of AI on e-commerce demand from customers' perspective

As we can see, more than 75% have acknowledged that using AI in e-commerce has molded the need in the last two years, also due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Based on the provided responses on a scale of 1-10 regarding the impact of implementing AI on e-commerce demand over the past 2 years, it seems that the majority of respondents rated the impact relatively high, with ratings clustered around 7 or 8. Some respondents gave lower ratings, particularly around 2-5, while others gave higher ratings of 9 or 10. This suggests that, overall, there is a perceived significant positive impact of implementing AI on e-commerce demand, although there is some variability in how respondents perceive this impact.

Conclusion

Future e-commerce applications of AI should grow as more companies recognize how important it is to shape customer preferences. Rapid advancements in research technology and more accessibility to the internet offer e-commerce companies a chance to grow their range of platforms. Notably, AI's impact on e-commerce extends to consumer satisfaction and retention. The changes and acceptance of AI in e-commerce are centred around the needs of the customers. As a result, e-commerce may create sophisticated customer relationship management systems and expand consumer contact. The study's researcher has produced a paper that offers a critical review of AI fundamental ideas and applications in e-commerce, along with a thorough understanding of how AI fits into the e-commerce sector's consumer needs. The finished study offers insightful information about consumer perceptions and experiences with (AI) and its effects on e-commerce. The study reveals that AI's integration into e-commerce significantly enhances the online shopping experience, influencing consumer behaviour and demand. Data indicates a widespread adoption of AI-driven features, such as personalized recommendations and chatbots, which are positively received by consumers. These technologies effectively increase engagement and conversion rates by offering tailored product suggestions and efficient customer support. Despite the general acceptance of AI, concerns persist regarding data privacy and the potential for biased recommendations. The impact of AI on e-commerce demand has been notably significant, particularly in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. Future strategies for e-commerce should focus on optimizing AI applications, addressing ethical concerns, and continuously improving consumer interactions to maintain a competitive edge and ensure a positive user experience.

The study concludes by highlighting the increasing impact of AI on e-commerce business outcomes and consumer behaviour. Although customers value the advantages of AI-driven personalization, e-commerce platforms must address privacy, bias, and personalization concerns in order to guarantee that AI technology is used in a way that is both beneficial and moral going forward.

References

1. Akpan, I. J., Udoh, E. A. P., & Adebisi, B. (2022). *Small business awareness and adoption of state-of-the-art technologies in emerging and developing markets, and lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic*. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 34*(2), 123–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08276331.2020.1820185>
2. Brynjolfsson, E., & McElheran, K. (2016). *The rapid adoption of artificial intelligence and its impact on business*. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 30*(3), 155–172. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.30.3.155>
3. Chui, M., Manyika, J., & Mire Madi, M. (2016). *Where machines could replace humans—and where they can't (yet)*. *McKinsey Quarterly*. Retrieved from

McKinsey.

4. Duan, Y., Edwards, J. S., & Dwivedi, Y. K. (2019). *Artificial intelligence for decision making in the era of Big Data – A research agenda*. *International Journal of Information Management*, 48,* 63–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.01.036>
5. Gams, M., & Kolenik, T. (2021). *Relations between electronics, artificial intelligence and information society through information society rules*. *Electronics*, 10*(4), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10040514>
6. Gielens, K., & Steenkamp, J.-B. E. M. (2019). *Branding in the era of digital (dis)intermediation*. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 36*(3), 367–384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijresmar.2019.01.005>
7. Hopkins, J., Kafali, Ö., Alrayes, B., & Stathis, K. (2019). *Pirasa: Strategic protocol selection for e-commerce agents*. *Electronic Markets*, 29*(2), 239–252. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-018-0307-4>
8. Kaplan, A., & Haenlein, M. (2019). *Siri, Siri, in my hand: Who's the fairest in the land? On the interpretations, illustrations, and implications of artificial intelligence*. *Business Horizons*, 62*(1), 15–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2018.08.004>
9. Klaus, T., & Changchit, C. (2019). *Toward an understanding of consumer attitudes on online review usage*. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 59*(3), 277–286. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08874417.2017.1348916>
10. Ransbotham, S., Candelon, F., LaFountain, B., & Kiron, D. (2020). *Artificial intelligence in business gets real: How AI is transforming business practices*. *MIT Sloan Management Review*. Retrieved from MIT Sloan.
11. Song, X., Yang, S., Huang, Z., & Huang, T. (2019). *The application of artificial intelligence in electronic commerce*. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1302*(3), 032030. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1302/3/032030>
12. Soni, N., Sharma, E. K., Singh, N., & Kapoor, A. (2020). *Artificial intelligence in business: From research and innovation to market deployment*. *Procedia Computer Science*, 167,* 2200–2210.
13. Wang, T. (2021). *Discussion on business models of Alibaba and Amazon in three operating directions*. *Frontiers in Economics and Management*, 2*(4), 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.6981/FEM.202104>